

Three-Dimensional Fabrics for Composites —An Introduction to the Magnaweave Structure

F. K. Ko

Philadelphia College of Textiles and Science, School House Lane and Henry Avenue, Philadelphia, PA 19144, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

The current status of 3-D fabric preforms is reviewed. Specifically, a 3-D preform manufactured by the Magnaweave process is presented. The Magnaweave structure, characterized by its integrated structural nature with an ability to form complex shapes, represents an attractive reinforcement concept for structural composites with a high level of interlaminar strength.

INTRODUCTION

Fabric preforms have become increasingly important as reinforcements for flexible and rigid composites in recent years due to the increase in consciousness in cost reduction and the demand for large structural composites with complex shapes [1,2].

The major weakness of the laminated 2-D preforms such as the woven fabrics is the lack of isotropy and poor interlaminar strength. The Z-direction strength which is required for structural composites can be improved by 3-D preforms. Over the last twenty to thirty years, several 3-D structures with multidirectional reinforcement have been developed. Most of the earlier developments are basically hand-made structures for heat shielding of the surface of reentry vehicles [3]. In recent years, worldwide emphasis in the development of 3-D structures has been placed on mechanization of the fabric formation process and the tailoring of the fabrics for various structural shapes [4,5,6,7]. The market development effort for the 3-D structures has expanded from pure aerospace to medical [7,8], and the attractive areas of structural composites for land and sea transportation, building and highway constructions.

In this paper, after a brief review of the current 3-D structures, the Magnaweave 3-D weaving technology is introduced.

A REVIEW OF 3-D FABRICS

Even though 3-D fabric weaving is perhaps as old as the textile art and craft industry, the serious use of 3-D fabrics for composites did not begin until we entered the space age. The earlier 3-D concepts are exemplified by the AVCO 3-D weave [9] and the various structures described by Adsit et al [3]. These

structures are either formed by weaving of yarns in three orthogonal directions, stitching or introducing preferentially oriented fiber bundles into filament wound or laminated systems. These 3-D structures were all designed to be ablative materials used in reentry vehicles.

The continuous development of 3-D structures into more commercial and mechanized processes are demonstrated by the FMI and Aerolor structures [10,4]. Figures 1A and 1B show the X-Y-Z orthogonal weaves in rectangular and cylindrical forms. Figure 1C shows a concept for multidirectional reinforcement. It has been shown that structures with over ten directions of reinforcement can be produced [10].

Interesting developments of 3-D structures have also been carried out at the Research Institute for Polymers and Textiles in Japan under the direction of Mr. Kenji Fukuta [7]. As shown in Figures 1D, E and F, the Fukuta 3-D structures range from rigid open orthogonal, rigid dense orthogonal structure to semi-integrated conformable 3-D constructions. These structures are being considered for building and highway construction as well as for artificial bone.

THE MAGNAWEAVE 3-D STRUCTURE

At the Textile Research Laboratory of the Philadelphia College of Textiles and Science, we have been involved in the development and evaluation of several preforms which include the Magnaweave structure. The Magnaweave structure is an extension of the General Electric Omniweave concept. The general procedure for the formation of the Magnaweave structure has been detailed in a U.S. patent issued to Dr. Robert Florentine [11].

Basically, the Magnaweave process is a general braiding process wherein the interlacing and orientation of yarns is achieved by an orthogonal shedding motion which is followed by a combing (or compacting) motion. This process allows a high degree of freedom in the control of material distribution and material orientation. Because of the generalized nature of this process, one can consider the conventional braiding a special case of the Magnaweave process.

While the orientation of the material in the Magnaweave structure can be controlled to some degree, what distinguishes the Magnaweave structure from other 3-D preforms is its integrated structural geometry and its ability to assume complex shapes. To facilitate design, analysis and manufacturing, computer codes have been developed at our laboratory for the Magnaweave structures. Figure 2A illustrates a computer plot of the integrated nature of the Magnaweave structure in an I-beam configuration. Figure 2B shows the orientation of one of the yarns in an isometric view. Besides the first Magnaweave I-beam preform, several other structural shapes including thin and thick panels, channel, hollow square and solid bars have been developed at our laboratory. Thick and thin walled cylinders have also been produced by the Atlantic Research Company. The materials which have been woven successfully with the Magnaweave process include E-glass, S-glass, graphite, Kevlar, silicon carbide, aluminum-coated fiberglass, aluminum-coated graphite and all the major textile fibers. Several pre-impregnated glass, graphite and Kevlar Magnaweave fabrics have also been prepared in our laboratory.

Preliminary tensile testing of the Magnaweave preform before impregnation showed that the material can be fabricated into the Magnaweave fabric with minimum damage to the material. As shown in Figure 3, the stress-strain behavior of the Magnaweave is remarkably similar to that of the component yarn before weaving. A sample of similar dimension manufactured in a conventional square braiding machine has considerably lower modulus and tensile strength than the Magnaweave fabric.

Resin matrix and metal matrix composite samples have also been prepared with the Magnaweave fabric. Table I shows a summary of preliminary test data comparing a Magnaweave fabric with conventional fiberglass laminate.

A, B, C - courtesy of Aerolor; D, E, F - courtesy of Mr. Fukuta

Figure 1. Some recent 3-D reinforcement concepts

Figure 2. Computer plot of Magnaweave I-Beam

Figure 3. Stress-Strain Behavior of Magnaweave and Square Braid

Table I. Comparison of Magnaweave with Commercial Composites

Fabric	Style 1581	MAGNA No. 1
Resin	F155	F155
% Resin	37%	27%
Flex Strength	88,000 psi	55,600 psi
Flex Modulus	3.4×10^6 psi	4.6×10^6 psi
Short Beam Shear	4,800 psi	8,200 psi

Courtesy - Dr. David Wood, Hexcel

Even though the resin content for the two composites are not the same, this preliminary data does indicate a higher level of flex modulus and a significantly higher level of shear strength. To evaluate the processibility of the Magnaweave for metal matrix composites, aluminum/graphite Magnaweave fabric was consolidated by Dr. Koczak of Drexel University using ion plating and vacuum hot pressing technique. Microstructures of the consolidated Magnaweave composites, as shown in Figure 4, indicate normal penetration of the metal matrix.

Considering the interesting characteristic of the Magnaweave preform, the potential applications of the Magnaweave structures being explored currently include resin and metal matrix composites for aerospace, land and sea transportation, building and highway construction, antiballistic and surgical implants.

CONCLUSIONS

A state of the art review of 3-D fabrics has been carried out which indicated the trend in the development of 3-D fabric has evolved from hand-made samples with limited shapes for very specialized ablative applications to machine-made complex shape preforms for a wide range of structural applications for the aerospace and civilian market.

A new process - the Magnaweave process - for the manufacturing of 3-D preforms has been introduced. This process is unique in its ability to control the material distribution and orientation, as well as the formation of a wide range of complex structural shapes in an integral manner. Most of the high performance fibers for resin matrix, metal matrix and ceramic matrix composites have been converted successfully into the Magnaweave preform. A superior inter-laminar strength is anticipated for the Magnaweave composites.

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400x

100x

1000x

AS CONSOLIDATED - LONGITUDINAL

300x

AS CONSOLIDATED - TRANSVERSE

Figure 4. Microstructure of aluminum/graphite composite

Courtesy - Dr. M. Koczak

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